

The New Way of Managing Sensitive Data

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INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 virus has changed the way citizens go about their daily lives in numerous ways. Keeping distance and wearing face masks in public transport are examples of basic measures everyone has to comply with (Rijksoverheid, n.d.). However, these measures alone will not be enough to contain the spread of the virus. According to the OECD (2020), timely, secure and reliable data access and sharing are crucial to understanding the virus and its spread. Many governments have turned to additional measures, such as technologies which collect, process and share data to further tackle the virus. While some of these technologies are effective at containing the virus, they have also proven themselves to be controversial in terms of their risk of violating privacy rights (OECD, 2020). For instance, contact-tracing technologies can provide important information to restrain the spread of the virus. If left unchecked however, this information can also be used for purposes such as collecting and sharing personal data, mass surveillance or limiting the freedom of citizens (OECD, 2020).

Especially with the advent of the European COVID-19 Data Platform, which enables rapid collection and sharing of research data (European Commission, 2020a), it is paramount to ensure that the way data is being handled at the moment has to be kept in check after the pandemic has subsided.

This paper will take a closer look at how the data policies of the Dutch government function during and after the pandemic. As most of the governments' data policies are publically available for everyone to read, desk research is used to analyze the way data is being handled. Additional information will be gathered through interviews with officials from local municipalities. Combining the gathered information will enable the research to further analyze the situation surrounding the Dutch data policy.

RESEARCH

Objective

Due to the COVID-19 outbreak, the Dutch government currently has access to a lot more private data than before (Privacy & COVID-19, 2020). This has enabled the government to monitor its civilians to trace the virus and put it under control. Inhabitants of the Netherlands are afraid of the information the Dutch government has access to and see this new data policy as a huge invasion of their privacy (Zarouali et al., 2020). Currently, it is unclear how the data policy will affect governmental data management. There is a lot of vagueness surrounding the risks and opportunities this policy entails. Creating more clarity about this issue by zooming in on the most significant changes this increased access to data will lead to is the main objective of this research.

Approach

This research will be split in two methods. The first part is desk research. During the desk research the data policies of the Dutch and other governments will be analyzed based on papers and government sites. Research will be done on which information is shared and how this data is protected. Additionally, trends from before, during and after the COVID-19 pandemic will be mapped out, so it will become clear which changes were made because of the COVID-19 pandemic and which changes were already set in motion.

The field research will take place in the form of interviews. Several officials, from local municipalities, will be interviewed about the data management changes during the current pandemic and which changes have been put into place due to the need to better monitor the population. Based on the gathered information, the benefits, drawbacks and risks of this policy will be analyzed. This analysis will lead to a recommendation on which decisions should be made by the government to ensure the renewed data policy will lead to as much benefit as possible without violating the privacy of the Dutch citizens.

GOVERNMENT & PUBLIC SERVICE

The pandemic has led to lots of new rules and regulations that were introduced at national and international level. In Europe, many new regulations were made by the European Union (EU). Countries that are involved in the EU made agreements to get through this pandemic. For example, a recovery fund has been introduced and some regulations regarding safety and finance were adjusted (Rijksoverheid, n.d.).

The way governments are exchanging information with private organizations and individuals has also changed. On February 19th 2020 the European Commission adopted its new Digital Strategy. Data plays a major role in tackling the COVID-19 virus. Many ways of handling the virus have been introduced. For instance, the European Commission has adopted a method in which mobile data is used to prevent the virus from spreading. It includes preventive measures, warnings and contact tracing. The European Commission has also introduced an EU toolbox for the use of mobile applications which includes requirements for apps that are being developed to tackle the virus (European Commission, n.d.). Lastly, the European Commission also introduced a sharing platform for researchers to enable the collection and sharing of all available research data (European Commission, 2020a).

To develop an effective and non-violating application, the countries in Europe need to take the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) into account. The GDPR states that health data is considered as sensitive data and therefore can only be used under strict requirements. If there is a legal ground, in this case the pandemic, health data may become available to develop an application. Thus, governments of countries in the EU may get access to data that was not accessible before the pandemic (European Commission, n.d.).

Even though the above measures could help prevent the virus from spreading, a lot of privacy and security concerns have been raised regarding the sharing of data. Private companies are reluctant to share data with researchers and governments due to protection and commercial issues. Besides, the sharing of data also raises public concerns about privacy, data protection and civil liberties. The key concern is that the data and information will be used to legitimize and create tools for surveillance which will be used by governments and technology companies after the pandemic (Oliver et al., 2020).

The mentioned concerns also apply to the Netherlands. The government wants to change the law to get access to telecom data. The country also introduced an application on a voluntary basis to keep track of the spreading of the virus (COVID-19Melder). Furthermore, several other rules and

regulations are in the process of changing with regard to the pandemic (Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens, n.d.).

ANALYSIS

IT Governance and Strategic Sourcing

Dutch municipalities collect and process a lot of personal data. This data is needed so that they can carry out their tasks, think of people moving in and out of the city, or people applying for a drivers license. Citizens are often even obligated to give certain personal information to their respective municipalities (DDPA, n.d.). When the government requires you to hand over sensitive information, it is expected that this information is handled with care.

To ensure data integrity, three laws have been introduced to decide how Dutch municipalities may use personal data (DDPA, n.d.). The most notable of these three laws is the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Generally speaking, this law has strengthened privacy rights, giving more responsibilities to organizations that handle sensitive data and made it possible for privacy regulators to fine violators for amounts up to 20 million euros (DDPA, n.d.).

However, with the coming of COVID-19, some of these data protection rules have taken a backseat for measures meant to limit the spread of the virus (Rijksoverheid, n.d.). The European Data Protection Board (EDPB) has even stated that any legislative measure can be introduced to safeguard public security as long as it constitutes a necessary, appropriate and proportionate measure within a democratic society (EDPB, 2020).

Even before the COVID-19 pandemic, municipalities have been struggling with implementing the GDPR. This is mainly because the GDPR contains open standards and does not provide any explanation for certain articles. Additionally, there are no case laws that could give a direction for organizations. This is especially true for the principle of privacy by design/default for processes, systems and applications for the rights of the involved (VNG, n.d.). COVID-19 has undoubtedly made it even more difficult to comply with the data protection rules for the Dutch municipalities.

Currently there are no major changes in the data management of the government. Personal data is still protected by the GDPR and the Dutch AVG (CMweb, n.d.). The government is using more real-time data to build and keep her COVID-19 dashboards up to date, the data of infected people is shared with the WHO (RIVM, n.d.). It could be stated that the current pandemic enabled more data sharing between the WHO and the governments, so that a more global approach could be designed.

A major change which occurred during the pandemic is the way the government gathers data on the streets. Since many police officers and other personnel did not feel safe to freely walk the streets, the government started experimenting with drones to monitor streets and warn about the COVID-19 rules which are in place right now (Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens, n.d.). It should be noted that the data gathered by these drones still need to follow the current rules in place (Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens, n.d.).

Currently there are little changes in the use of data other than the government is trying to gather more real time data and using new technologies to gather it. However the government is trying to endorse an emergency law. This law would allow the government to analyze all data gathered by telecommunication companies and use it to monitor her civilians, to check who came in contact with the COVID-19 virus (Keijzer, 2020).

Officials active in the municipality of The Hague do agree that there has been a shift from influence on IT within the government. Since the COVID-19 outbreak started, the government gave more emergency influence to local governments which themselves decided which applications they deemed more useful for fighting the COVID-19 virus. So it could be stated that the input for applications has shifted from the business monarchy to a federal system. The current pandemic also increased the amount of data shared between municipalities and the central government integrating more and different data from local governments than before.

Figure 1. (Larger image in appendix)

Figure 1 describes data governance through several stages in time. Before the GDPR was introduced, each country in the EU had in place its own legislation to govern data protection. This caused a lack of harmonization within the European Union (Stefanouli, M., & Economou, C., 2018). In addition, there were no guidelines about what is permitted and what is not. Organizations started to collect huge amounts of data without properly informing the client and asking them for permission (Conrad, S. S., & Alghamdi, M. 2019). Clients were

not able to opt-out, or to be digitally ‘removed’ once they had registered on a particular website (Aridor, G., Che, Y. K., & Salz, T., 2020). To conclude, online behavior and data management was not deemed important enough to make sufficient unified legislation. Until 2016, when the GDPR was adopted and became enforceable May 2018.

The GDPR contains several pillars that organizations (profit and non-profit) should adhere to (see Figure 1). Data can only be processed if there is one or more legal reasons to do so according to article 6 of the GDPR:

- If consent has been given to use data
- To fulfil contractual obligations
- To comply with a data controller's legal obligations
- To protect the vital interests of a someone
- To perform a task in the public interest or in official authority
- For the legitimate interests of a data controller or a third party

These conditions to use data match the pillars as can be seen in Figure 1. Several scientists however, have criticized the GDPR with respect to the current COVID-19 crisis. Concerns persist that the GDPR has made organizations risk-averse in terms of data sharing, even if the regulation permits such sharing. Health care organizations focusing on individual risk minimization threaten to undermine COVID-19 research efforts (McLennan, S., Celi, L. A., & Buyx, A. 2020).

This goes against the purpose of the GDPR, as can be seen in the conditions on when to share/process data. especially when looking at the condition: ‘to perform a task in the public interest or in official authority.’

This turns out to be a difficult topic. J. A. Bovenberg, an attorney at law, argued that the current interpretations of GDPR fail to recognize that personal data is used in biomedical research to derive generalized knowledge that benefits society and is applied in ways that pose negligible privacy risks to data subjects. Consequently, he suggest the balance between an individual’s privacy and the benefit to society in research contexts is quite different from others. To conclude, the phrase: ‘public interest’ is subjective, and left to someone’s own interpretation.

Going forward after the COVID-19 crisis, it could very well be that changes in the GDPR regulation are inevitable. Perhaps it is not about changes in content, but rather the context, McLennan, Celi and Buyx already conducted a research and came up with a framework on how to interpret and implement GDPR in a way that does not hinder but actually fosters solving the COVID-19 pandemic.

Business Process Integration

This paragraph explains how the government exchanges information about the spread of COVID-19. The main rule in the Netherlands is that government information is publicly accessible, unless there are legal restrictions that decide otherwise. These exceptions are included in the ‘Wet Openbaarheid van Bestuur’ (WoB), or in English: ‘The Government Information Public Access Act’ (de Greef, R. J. M. H., 2018). The fact that a lot of information is available for everyone does not mean that it is not well protected.

Data management has become increasingly important during the COVID-19 outbreak as it can help trace the virus, making rapid data sharing the basis for public health action (Moorthy, V. et al. 2020). The Government gathering and analyzing data is not a new phenomenon. Take for example Centraal Bureau Statistiek (CBS), which shows statistical trends in a multitude of topics.

A significant change in a Governmental data management process due to COVID-19 is the daily data collection for the COVID-19 Virus Dashboard. This dashboard is created by the government in cooperation with RIVM, GGD and hospitals and is meant for the government and civilians to keep an overview of the current status of the pandemic per region of the Netherlands (Rijksoverheid, 2020).

As said before, gathering data by the government is not new. New however, is the frequency of the data collection. The dashboard is updated every day to ensure that municipalities can take local measures when needed. Figure 2 below shows what the process is of data collection to compose the dashboard in an activity diagram, a bigger diagram can be found in the appendix. As you can see, the data is being collected from the RIVM, GGD and Hospitals. After the collection of the data from these three actors, the dashboard can be updated daily (Rijksoverheid, n.d.). The actors involved in this process are also shown in the use case diagram in figure 3 a bigger diagram can be found in the appendix.

New features are added to the dashboard every other time. So, the dashboard is still in the development phase. New features include the estimated number of contagious people and the results of sewage water measurements (Rijksoverheid, 2020). To keep adding new features, the government needs to employ people with the right skills like developers and data scientists. Also, to update the dashboard daily with current and accurate data, the government and its data and information providers (RIVM, GGD and Hospitals), need to work fast and agile. This last point is difficult for the government because the organization lacks the ability to change their processes during new circumstances.

Figure 2. (Larger image in appendix)

Figure 3. (Larger image in appendix)

Due to the bureaucratic nature and political behaviour of the organization, change in processes can't be adapted quickly (Schuijt, 2018). This could cause problems and inaccuracy during the development and data collection of the COVID-19 Virus Dashboard.

Cyber Security

For this risk assessment, the top three existing threats from the Cyber Security Assessment Netherlands (National Coordinator for Security and Counterterrorism, 2019) will be reevaluated using an impact score from 1 to 5 (negligible to severe) and a likelihood score from 1 to 5 (very unlikely to very likely). This will give a general overview of the impact of COVID-19 on the cybersecurity of the

Dutch government. These scores can be multiplied to give a total risk score which determines the overall risk score. Following a table by Katsumata, Hemenway and Gavins (2010), these total risk scores can be high to low. The rest of the threats and additional information on cyber security for the Dutch Government can be found in the appendix.

Risk 1: Espionage carried out by states or state-affiliated actors

<i>Impact</i>	4
<i>Likelihood</i>	5
<i>Total</i>	20

The risk of espionage carried out by state or state-affiliated actors was already colored red in the threat matrix, and it is expected to stay high as the risk is focused on espionage. The espionage is focused on gaining information for a country's geopolitical, economic and military interest, and as the European Commission and the Netherlands are focused on sharing more data, there will be a larger attack surface for the actors. As the impact of espionage is not mentioned to have the most impact, but the overall threat is deemed to be high in the assessment of the NCTV (2019), the impact will be significant and the likelihood will be very likely as more countries are increasing their focus on espionage.

Measures: Data encryption, multi-factor authentication & control access.

Risk 2: Data manipulation carried out by states or state-affiliated actors

<i>Impact</i>	4
<i>Likelihood</i>	4
<i>Total</i>	16

The risk of data manipulation carried out by states or state-affiliated actors is expected to be high. In the assessment of the NCTV (2019) it is stated that data manipulation can have a substantial impact on the integrity of data and with the increasing threat of states or state-affiliated actors likelihood will be high. For these actors the access to databases can become easier with these larger attack surfaces, but it is not mentioned as their highest interest. Whether the impact of this threat changes due to COVID-19 is questionable as COVID-19 data might not be data of their highest interest.

Measures: Control access, assign roles (restriction on handling data), back-up files & data encryption.

Risk 3: Disruption carried out by criminals

<i>Impact</i>	5
<i>Likelihood</i>	4
<i>Total</i>	20

The risk of disruption carried out by criminals is also mentioned to be high in the assessment. Due to COVID-19 this risk is expected to still be high. Disruption is mentioned in the assessment of the NCTV (2019) to have the highest impact and the likelihood is also high. With the need for integrated data sharing platforms and data to see the development surrounding COVID-19, accessibility will be very important. This leads to a severe impact on society when such an event will take place.

Measures: Security breach detection, system resilience & system continuity.

DISCUSSION

In the results we identified different types of transformations during COVID-19 within the government. The IT Governance perspective shows that the government is gathering more data than before. It also shows that there is more real time data used to monitor the COVID-19 virus, but the gathered data is still protected following the GDPR and no unauthorized personnel has access to this data. Also, the government is trying to implement a new law which enables them to get access to more personal data to combat the COVID-19 virus, but there have been no further developments in this process. A new change is the way the government manages IT. In the past the central government was in charge of most of the IT of municipalities, but because of the pandemic many municipalities attained more control in which applications they would use to combat the virus. it could thus be stated that the IT governance has shifted from a business hierarchy perspective, to a federal perspective.

The Business Process Integration perspective shows that the process and frequency of the data collection has changed. Different actors are included in the data collection phase of the process. As the corona dashboard is new, the government created a process that is relatively new as it is working towards a new goal. The charging of information between different governmental departments and public services is not new, but the way it is done creates a new process. The dashboard is updated daily. Also, new features are still being added to the dashboard. However the dashboard is useful to keep track of the spread of the virus, there could be implications now and in the future. Many privacy issues were raised when the dashboard was developed (Redactie, 2020). There is a risk that sensitive information that is being collected by the government will be leaked or misused, which has happened before (RTLnieuws, 2020). The information that is being collected about the spread of the virus also raises implications on the governance side because of the GDPR legislation. This is due to all the privacy-sensitive data that is collected of citizens (AP, 2020).

The Cyber Security perspective shows that, due to COVID-19, changes will take place that can threaten the cyber security of the Dutch government, in particular threats related to data sharing and collecting. As digitization increases the surface for actors to attack, it is important for the Dutch government to keep a close eye on how systems are interconnected and on the way data is shared between different systems. This comes with great complexity and the defense against cyber risks will become harder (National Coordinator for Security and Counterterrorism, 2019). Regarding the three risks ranked highest in the risk assessment, it will be extremely important to establish an effective security environment surrounding the data sharing platforms, both on national and international level. As both the Netherlands and the European Commission want to enable more data sharing for future benefits, cyber security will need to be sufficient to protect the increasing attack surface against different actors. Furthermore, the Dutch government will have to focus on digital resilience. This resilience needs to be in place to enable business continuity in case of an undesirable event. This is particularly important during the COVID-19 crisis, not just for the government as an organization but also for their citizens to ensure the accessibility and trustworthiness of the governmental online services.

CONCLUSION

It is important to realize that the COVID-19 crisis is still happening at this very moment and will not disappear for the foreseeable future. The same goes for the digital transformation of the government. Any findings and any recommendations given in this report are subject to change. That change being the severity of the crisis. When this report was created, COVID-19 was roughly speaking dormant. However, by the time the report was finalized, the situation had deteriorated. It is hard to keep up with an ever changing situation, and we have found this is no different for the data management of the Dutch Government.

On a BPI point of view, the importance of a smooth data collection process has never been more important. A brand new COVID-19 Dashboard was built from the ground up, combining new and existing data from different sources. The government is well on its way to increase the frequency of the data loads, almost reaching a real time situation to help the government to not be overtaken by events.

This nifty dashboard sounds like a perfect solution to measure the status of COVID-19. However, on a cybersecurity perspective, there are serious risks. Data manipulation by ill-intentioned

people is hard to detect and can paint a wrong picture. The same goes for the governance behind the dashboard. Citizens are worried of what will happen with personal data that has to be made available due to the crisis.

So to conclude, we can definitely say that the digital transformation of the government is still going on as we speak. It is recommended to keep the IT structure behind the dashboard (and other digital COVID-19 solutions) loose and flexible, but to not lose sight of the governance behind it. In the future other sources might be needed instead of the ones used today. A plug-and-play environment needs to be created to ensure a realistic view of the current situation, to take appropriate measures.

‘The enemy is never more unnerving than when he is invisible’

~ K. J. Parker

REFERENCES

- Ackerman, G., & Peterson, H. (2020, June). Terrorism and COVID-19: Actual and Potential Impacts. *Perspectives on Terrorism*, 14(3), 59-73.
- Algemene Rekenkamer. (2019, May 15). *Rijksoverheid heeft informatiebeveiliging en IT beheer nog niet op orde*. Retrieved September 27, 2020, from Algemene Rekenkamer: <https://www.rekenkamer.nl/actueel/nieuws/2019/05/15/rijksoverheid-heeft-informatiebeveiliging-en-it-beheer-nog-niet-op-orde>
- AP.(2020,april, 17). Retrieved from: <https://autoriteitpersoonsgegevens.nl/nl/nieuws/ap-toetst-opzet-COVID-19-apps>
- Aridor, G., Che, Y. K., & Salz, T. (2020). The Economic Consequences of Data Privacy Regulation: Empirical Evidence from GDPR (No. w26900). National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Autoriteit persoonsgegevens (n.d.). *Cameratoezicht op openbare plaatsen*. retrieved from: <https://autoriteitpersoonsgegevens.nl/nl/onderwerpen/foto-en-film/cameratoezicht-op-openbare-plaatsen#mag-ik-als-gemeente-drones-of-rijdende-camera%E2%80%99s-inzetten-7757>
- Autoriteit persoonsgegevens (2020). *Privacy & COVID-19*. retrieved from: <https://autoriteitpersoonsgegevens.nl/nl/onderwerpen/COVID-19/privacy-COVID-19>
- CM (2020). *COVID-19 en de AVG: dit zijn de regels*. Retrieved from: <https://cmweb.nl/2020/03/COVID-19-en-avg-dit-zijn-de-regels/>

Conrad, S. S., & Alghamdi, M. (2019). What GDPR means for data privacy. *Journal of Computing Sciences in Colleges*, 34(3), 133-133.

de Bruijne, M., van Eeten, M., Gañán, C. H., & Pieters, W. (2017). *Towards a new cyber threat actor typology*. Retrieved from Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek- en Documentatiecentrum: https://wodc.nl/binaries/2740_Summary_tcm28-273244.pdf

de Greef, R. J. M. H. (2018). Openbaarheid van bestuur en intergemeentelijke samenwerking: Hoe zit het nu eigenlijk?. *De Gemeentestem*, 2018(7478), 682-695.

Digital Government. (2019). *NL DIGITAAL: Data Agenda Government*. Retrieved from <https://www.nldigitalgovernment.nl/wp-content/uploads/sites/11/2019/04/data-agenda-government.pdf>

Digital Government. (2020). *NL DIGIbeter 2020*.

European Commission. (2020a). *COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS*. Brussels.

European Commission. (n.d.). *Digital*. Retrieved September 23, 2020, from European Commission: https://ec.europa.eu/info/live-work-travel-eu/health/COVID-19virus-response/digital_en

European Commission. (2020b). *INCEPTION IMPACT ASSESSMENT*. Retrieved from <https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/12491-Legislative-framework-for-the-governance-of-common-European-data-spaces>

Government of the Netherlands. (2018). *Dutch Digitalisation Strategy*. Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy.

Janssen, M., Wimmer, M. A., & Deljoo, A. (Eds.). (2015). *Policy practice and digital science : integrating complex systems, social simulation and public administration in policy research* (Ser. Public administration and information technology, volume 10). Springer. <https://doi-org.tilburguniversity.idm.oclc.org/10.1007/978-3-319-12784-2>

Katsumata, P., Hemenway, J., & Gavins, W. (2010). Cybersecurity Risk Management. *The 2010*

Military Communications Conference, (pp. 890-895). San Jose.

Klonowska, K., & Bindt, P. (2020). *The COVID-19 pandemic:: two waves of technological responses in the European Union*. Hague Centre for Strategic Studies.

KPMG. (2020). *COVID-19virus and Cyber Security*. Retrieved from Deltalinqs.

McLennan, S., Celi, L. A., & Buyx, A. (2020). COVID-19: Putting the General Data Protection Regulation to the Test. *JMIR public health and surveillance*, 6(2), e19279. <https://doi.org/10.2196/19279>

Moorthy, V., Restrepo, A. M. H., Preziosi, M. P., & Swaminathan, S. (2020). Data sharing for novel COVID-19virus (COVID-19). *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*, 98(3), 150.

National Coordinator for Security and Counterterrorism. (2019). *The Cyber Security Assessment Netherlands*.

National Cyber Security Centre. (2018). *National Cyber Security Agenda*.

Redactie. (2020). *Een lokaal COVID-19 dashboard: noodzakelijk of schending van de privacy?* Retrieved from: <https://www.at5.nl/artikelen/204058/een-lokaal-COVID-19dashboard-noodzakelijk-of-schending-van-de-privacy>

Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu. (n.d.). Retrieved September 26, 2020, from Databronnen COVID-19: <https://www.databronnencovid19.nl/>

Rijksoverheid. (2020) *COVID-19 dashboard verder uitgebreid*. Retrieved from: <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/actueel/nieuws/2020/07/02/COVID-19dashboard-verder-uitgebreid>

Rijksoverheid. (n.d.). *Dashboard COVID-19virus*. Retrieved From: <https://COVID-19dashboard.rijksoverheid.nl/over>

Rijksoverheid. (n.d.). *Hoe zorgt de overheid ervoor dat COVID-19Melder veilig is?* Retrieved 09 26, 2020, from Rijksoverheid: <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/onderwerpen/COVID-19virus-app/vraag-en-antwoord/hoe-zorgt-de-overheid-ervoor-dat-de-COVID-19-app-veilig-is>

RIVM (2020). *Databronnen COVID-19*. Retrieved from: <https://www.databronnenCOVID->

1919.nl/Bron?naam=COVID-19virus-Disease-Situation-Dashboard

RTLnieuws.(2020). *Infectieradar van RIVM tijdelijk offline na datalek*. Retrieved from: <https://www.rtlnieuws.nl/tech/artikel/5145451/infectieradar-rivm-datalek>

Schuijt.(2018). *Als veranderingen niet van de grond komen*. Retrieved from: <https://www.managementsite.nl/verandermanagement-overheid-als-veranderingen-vastlopen>

Stefanouli, M., & Economou, C. (2018, May). Data Protection in Smart Cities: Application of the EU GDPR. In The 4th Conference on Sustainable Urban Mobility (pp. 748-755). Springer, Cham.

Tweede Kamer (2020). *Tijdelijke wet informatieverstrekking RIVM in verband met COVID-19*. retrieved from: <https://www.tweedekamer.nl/kamerstukken/wetsvoorstellen/detail?cfg=wetsvoorstel details&qry=wetsvoorstel%3A35479>

Zurier, S. (2020, April 4). *DARKReading*. Retrieved September 27, 2020, from Could Return of Ghost Squad Hackers Signal Rise in COVID-19-Related Hactivism?: <https://www.darkreading.com/attacks-breaches/could-return-of-ghost-squad-hackers-signal-rise-in-COVID-19-related-hactivism/d/id/1337588>

APPENDIX

Term Paper Cyber Security

Sharing data on a European and Dutch level

The COVID-19 virus crisis shines a new light on the adoption of the Digital Strategy developed by the European Commission, as the need for online connectivity grows. (European Commission, sd). But to create this digital transformation and connectivity, the European Commission needs to tackle the threats that arise due to these plans. To help governments in the making of policies surrounding COVID-19, the sharing of data will be very important. For governments to make appropriate policies, they are dependent on data about the current situations and policies (Janssen, Wimmer, & Deljoo, 2015). Since proactive information-sharing becomes more important to monitor the developments surrounding COVID-19, tackling these risks becomes more important.

On July 1st 2018, the government of the Netherlands already filed a report on the Dutch Digitalization Strategy. One of the focus areas of

this digitalization strategy is to enhance the sharing of data, not only within sectors, but also between sectors (Government of the Netherlands, 2018). This sharing of data becomes also increasingly important to improve the process of policy making for the Dutch government. The government wants to use a more data-driven approach to solve the problems they are facing. As a part of this approach, the government wants to smoothen the transition of conversion that needs to take place to add data from municipalities in the national data sets (Digital Government, 2019).

Even though the Netherlands was already focused on digitalization, COVID-19 and the digitalization strategy of the European Commission requested even more focus on the process of digitization. This can be seen in the report the Dutch Digital Government published in June 2020 (Digital Government, 2020). Due to COVID-19 there will be more focus on the access to and trustworthiness of the digital services of the government.

Cyber security for the Dutch government

In terms of cyber security for the Netherlands, the National Cyber Security Centre of the Ministry of Justice and Security of the Netherlands published a National Cyber Security Agenda (NCSA) in 2018 (National Cyber Security Centre, 2018). The NCSA discusses their seven ambitions that should help in achieving their main objective: “*The Netherlands is capable of capitalizing on the economic and social opportunities of digitalisation in a secure way and of protecting national security in the digital domain.*” Furthermore, the NCSA also discusses different threats that could lead to damage for national security, especially since cybersecurity is linked to the national security of the Netherlands in an inextricable way. This inextricable link influences the development of the digital processes of the Dutch government, as these processes need to meet cybersecurity requirements.

Just before the COVID-19 crisis started, the National Coordinator for Security and Counterterrorism (NCTV) published The Cyber Security Assessment Netherlands (National Coordinator for Security and Counterterrorism, 2019). In this assessment they published a threat matrix in which only threats are displayed that are estimated to be carried out by actors who have sufficient capacities and intentions or actors from which they know that they carried out such activities in the past. This threat matrix is based on a publication by de Bruijne et al. (2017). The different threats are colored in either red, orange or yellow, assuming to be a high, medium or low threat level. For the government, the following threats are identified in the assessment:

- Espionage carried out by states or state-

affiliated actors (high), meaning these actors copy or remove data which impairs the confidentiality of information.

- Data manipulation carried out by states or state-affiliated actors (high), meaning these actors edit data with intention which impairs the integrity of information.
- Disruption carried out by criminals (high), meaning these criminals intentionally disrupt the accessibility of data or information systems or services which temporarily impairs the accessibility.
- System manipulation carried out by criminals (medium), meaning these criminals target the confidentiality or integrity of information systems or services which impairs these systems or services.
- Disruption carried out by cyber vandals and script kiddies (medium), meaning these actors intentionally disrupt the accessibility of data or information systems or services which temporarily impairs accessibility.
- Disruption/failure caused by unintentional acts (medium), meaning the accessibility is disrupted by unintentional acts like human error, technical problems or natural causes.
- Data theft carried out by criminals (low), meaning these criminals copy or remove data which impairs the confidentiality of information.
- Sabotage carried out by terrorists (low), meaning these terrorists intentionally disrupt the accessibility of data or information systems or services which impairs accessibility in a very long-lasting manner. This can possibly lead to destruction.
- Disruption carried out by hackers (low), meaning these hackers intentionally disrupt the accessibility of data or information systems or services which temporarily impairs the accessibility.
- Data theft by insiders (low), meaning these insiders copy or remove data which impairs the confidentiality of information.
- Data leak caused by unintentional acts (low), meaning the leak of data that is caused by unintentional acts like human error, technical problems or natural causes impairs the confidentiality.

As these threats are established before the start of COVID-19, it is important to look at how the likelihood and impact of these threats are changed due to COVID-19. Especially with the integration of a single market for data in the European Union which establishes data flows between countries (European Commission, 2020a). The European Commission already performed an impact assessment on the legislative actions to create such

a single market (European Commission, 2020a). It discusses the likely impact that the potential new rules for common European data spaces can have on different areas, like economically and socially. The planned legislative framework might be put into place to tackle problems concerning the availability of data and ascertain requests to public sector organizations on use of data. The European Commission wants to tackle these problems to make the exchange of data easier and to make protected data available, conditional on the respect of rights of others. To do so, there have to be relevant standards and trusted technical infrastructures. This all can have an impact on how the Dutch government processes their data, as well as laws and regulations surrounding the processing of data.

Other big factors that come into play due to COVID-19, are the increased use of governmental services online and increased pressure on national data collection. Especially the data collection and sharing happening to map out the development of COVID-19 (Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu, sd), requests for extra cybersecurity as data need to be shared between different platforms. Also contact tracing apps, like COVID-19Melder for the Netherlands, request a lot of attention to protect the privacy of users without knowing whether the benefits weigh out the costs (Klonowska & Bindt, 2020). KPMG published a report on the relation between the COVID-19 virus and cyber security (KPMG, 2020). One of the issues related to the cyber security of the Dutch government according to KPMG, is the increase of spear-phishing attacks related to COVID-19 by cyber criminals. These phishing attacks, among other things, can try to collect financial and tax information of victims of these attacks by posing as a government agency. Also with the increased number of people working from home, accessibility to systems will be more important. These factors need to be taken into account when creating a new risk matrix.

Risk assessment following COVID-19

For this risk assessment, the existing threats from the Cyber Security Assessment Netherlands (National Coordinator for Security and Counterterrorism, 2019) will be reevaluated using an impact score from 1 to 5 (negligible to severe) and a likelihood score from 1 to 5 (very unlikely to very likely). This will give a general overview of the impact of COVID-19 on the cybersecurity of the Dutch government. These scores can be multiplied to give a total risk score which determines the overall risk score. Following a table by Katsumata, Hemenway and Gavins (2010), these total risk scores can be high to low.

		Impact				
		Negligible	Minor	Moderate	Significant	Severe
Likelihood	Very likely	L	M	H	H	H
	Likely	L	M	M	H	H
	Possible	L	L	M	M	H
	Unlikely	L	L	L	M	M
	Very Unlikely	L	L	L	L	M

Risk 1: Espionage carried out by states or state-affiliated actors

<i>Impact</i>	4
<i>Likelihood</i>	5
<i>Total</i>	20

The risk of espionage carried out by state or state-affiliated actors was already colored red in the threat matrix, and it is expected to stay high as the risk is focused on espionage. The espionage is focused on gaining information for a country's geopolitical, economical and military interest, and as the European Commission and the Netherlands are focused on sharing more data, there will be a larger attack surface for the actors. As the impact of espionage is not mentioned to have the most impact, but the overall threat is deemed to be high in the assessment of the NCTV (2019), the impact will be significant and the likelihood will be very likely as more countries are increasing their focus on espionage.

Measures: Data encryption, multi-factor authentication & control access.

Risk 2: Data manipulation carried out by states or state-affiliated actors

<i>Impact</i>	4
<i>Likelihood</i>	4
<i>Total</i>	16

The risk of data manipulation carried out by states or state-affiliated actors is expected to be high. In the assessment of the NCTV (2019) it is stated that data manipulation can have a substantial impact on the integrity of data and with the increasing threat of states or state-affiliated actors likelihood will be high. For these actors the access to databases can become easier with these larger attack surfaces, but it is not mentioned as their highest interest. Whether

the impact of this threat changes due to COVID-19 is questionable as COVID-19 data might not be data of their highest interest. *Measures: Control access, assign roles (restriction on handling data), back-up files & data encryption.*

Risk 3: Disruption carried out by criminals

<i>Impact</i>	5
<i>Likelihood</i>	4
<i>Total</i>	20

The risk of disruption carried out by criminals is also mentioned to be high in the assessment. Due to COVID-19 this risk is expected to still be high. Disruption is mentioned in the assessment of the NCTV (2019) to have the highest impact and the likelihood is also high. With the need for integrated data sharing platforms and data to see the development surrounding COVID-19, accessibility will be very important. This leads to a severe impact on society when such an event will take place. *Measures: Security breach detection, system resilience & system continuity.*

Risk 4: System manipulation carried out by criminals

<i>Impact</i>	3
<i>Likelihood</i>	3
<i>Total</i>	9

The risk of system manipulation carried out by criminals is expected to be medium. Likelihood will be possible as the governmental systems are becoming more attractive to use in cyber attacks on other targets. But following the assessment of the NCTV (2019), the impact will be minor as it mainly impacts the trust in digital society by citizens in a negative manner. In the context of COVID-19 the impact will be moderate as more people are dependent on these systems, from government employees to citizens using governmental services online. *Measures: Security breach detection, system resilience & system continuity.*

Risk 5: Disruption carried out by cyber vandals and script kiddies

<i>Impact</i>	3
<i>Likelihood</i>	3
<i>Total</i>	9

The risk of disruption carried out by cyber vandals and script kiddies is expected to be medium. As most attacks of cyber vandals and script kiddies are aimed at organizations it is possible that such an attack will happen. Even though disruption is said to have the highest impact according to the assessment of the NCTV (2019), the impact will be estimated to

be moderate as these disruptions are caused by actors who are not professional criminals, so a lower impact. Taking into account the importance of accessibility due to COVID-19, the impact is still expected to be moderate as it only temporarily influences the accessibility.
Measures: Security breach detection, system resilience & system continuity.

Risk 6: Disruption/failure caused by unintentional acts

<i>Impact</i>	3
<i>Likelihood</i>	4
<i>Total</i>	12

The risk of disruption/failure caused by unintentional acts is expected to be medium. It is stated in the assessment of the NCTV (2019) that disruption and failure by unintentional acts is a major threat and this threat only increases due to systems being more interconnected and complex. With the impact of the measures surrounding COVID-19 and the need for more data sharing, systems become even more interconnected. This means it will be expected to be more likely of such an event happening.
Measures: Security breach detection, system resilience & system continuity.

Risk 7: Data theft carried out by criminals

<i>Impact</i>	4
<i>Likelihood</i>	1
<i>Total</i>	4

The risk of data theft carried out by criminals will be low. According to the assessment of the NCTV (2019), cyber criminals are more frequently focused on botnets and crypto miners. KPMG already observed an increase of infrastructure use for data theft by criminals in the form of phishing (KPMG, 2020), but this is more directed to citizens instead of the government. This is why the likelihood is expected to be very unlikely. The impact is possible as the stolen data could consist of personal data or for example technical information that can be used in future attacks.
Measures: Data encryption, multi-factor authentication & control access.

Risk 8: Sabotage carried out by terrorists

<i>Impact</i>	5
<i>Likelihood</i>	1
<i>Total</i>	5

The risk of sabotage carried out by terrorists is expected to be medium. In the assessment of the NCTV (2019) it is stated that sabotage has the most impact, but there will be no intent on executing any

form of sabotage as the threat of terrorists cyber attacks have been low for some years. It also states that terrorists are more focused on physical attacks, the COVID-19 crisis could have an influence on these types of terrorist attacks in the long run. Especially the second-order effects that could arise due to COVID-19 like a negative economic impact on the incomes of citizens could lead to an increase in recruitment of terrorists and radicalization (Ackerman & Peterson, 2020).
Measures: Security breach detection, system resilience & system continuity.

Risk 9: Disruption carried out by hacktivists

<i>Impact</i>	4
<i>Likelihood</i>	1
<i>Total</i>	4

The risk of disruption carried out by hacktivists is expected to be low. In 2019, no substantial attacks were detected carried out by hacktivists according to the assessment of NCTV (21019). The likelihood is expected to stay very unlikely even with the circumstances that come with COVID-19 (Zurier, 2020). As accessibility will become more important for the government due to COVID-19 to use the systems for data sharing, the impact will increase.
Measures: Security breach detection, system resilience & system continuity.

Risk 10: Data theft by insiders

<i>Impact</i>	5
<i>Likelihood</i>	2
<i>Total</i>	10

The risk of data theft by insiders is expected to be medium. The impact of data theft by insiders is expected to be higher in comparison to criminals as these insiders know which information can be critical and influence the decisions made by the government. Especially with the uncertainty of the economic future due to COVID-19, the likelihood of such an event happening can increase (KPMG, 2020). In the assessment of the NCTV (2019) it is said that the threat of insiders has decreased for the year before the assessment was released. But following the report of KPMG (2020) financial stress or uncertainty of their job can lead to employees being an insider threat. That is why the likelihood for this assessment is said to be unlikely.
Measures: Security breach detection, assign roles on data access, system resilience & system continuity.

Risk 11: Data leak caused by unintentional acts

<i>Impact</i>	2
<i>Likelihood</i>	4
<i>Total</i>	8

The risk of data leak caused by unintentional acts is expected to be medium. As mentioned before, threats caused by unintentional acts increase due to the growing complexity of the systems. Most of these data leaks were caused by human error (National Coordinator for Security and Counterterrorism, 2019). The complexity of systems and movement of data is expected to grow as new data sharing platforms are being established. This is expected to lead to a heightened likelihood of such an event happening. The impact is expected to be minor as the change of this data leak being related to critical data is minor expecting the government has secured the data in a sufficient manner. The assessment of the NCTV (2019) mentions that more than half of these data leaks were in the form of distributing personal data to the wrong person or distributing the wrong personal data. *Measures: Data encryption, training on data handling.*

Commission want to enable more data sharing for future benefits, cyber security will need to be sufficient to protect the increasing attack surface against criminals, states and state-affiliated actors.

Especially with the rapid need for data, due to COVID-19 (European Commission, 2020b), the European Commission and the Dutch government must not settle for less cyber security for these newly established data spaces. As these spaces can contain privacy sensitive information on the development on COVID-19, security will be important, as well as transparency on the use of personal data and the rules and regulations established to enable these types of data sharing. Even within the European Union not all countries have the same rules and practices surrounding a single market for data, which need to be implemented to ensure a safe and secure way of data handling (European Commission, 2020b).

Furthermore, the Dutch government will have to focus on digital resilience. “The increasing complexity and connectivity of the ICT landscape is putting more and more pressure on resilience levels. Boosting resilience is the most important means of reducing risk to citizens, businesses and government bodies” (National Coordinator for Security and Counterterrorism, 2019). Even though the NCTV mentions the importance of resilience, it also mentions that resilience is lagging. In May 2019 it was established that still eleven central government organizations had a data security level that was insufficient, this was even worse than the year before (Algemene Rekenkamer, 2019). This resilience needs to be in place to enable business continuity in case of an undesirable event. This is particularly important during the COVID-19 crisis, not just for the government as an organization but also for their citizens to ensure the accessibility and trustworthiness of the governmental online services.

		Impact				
		Negligible	Minor	Moderate	Significant	Severe
Likelihood	Very likely				Risk 1	
	Likely		Risk 11	Risk 6	Risk 2	Risk 3
	Possible			Risk 4 Risk 5		
	Unlikely					Risk 10
	Very Unlikely				Risk 7 Risk 9	Risk 8

Recommendations

As digitization increases the surface for actors to attack, it is important for the Dutch government to keep a close eye on how systems are interconnected and on how data is shared between different systems. This comes with great complexity and the defense against cyber risks will become harder (National Coordinator for Security and Counterterrorism, 2019). Regarding the three risks ranked highest in the risk assessment, it will be extremely important to establish an effective security environment surrounding the data sharing platforms, both on national and international level. As both the Netherlands and the European

Questions Municipality of the Hague

1. Hoe gingen jullie voorheen met persoonlijke data om, waar moesten jullie rekening mee houden?
2. Welke gegevens kunnen jullie van bewoners van de gemeente in zien?
3. hebben jullie meer bevoegdheden gekregen om data in te zien?
4. Tot welke data hebben jullie toegang en hebben jullie nu meer toegang of moeten jullie nu data op een bepaald manier krijgen?
5. Wie maakte de meeste IT beslissingen voor COVID-19?
6. Wie maakt de meeste IT beslissingen op dit moment om COVID-19 te bestrijden?

Activity diagram BPI

Use case diagram BPI

Several stages of IT Governance

